

A FOUNDATION FOR EQUITY

Evaluating A Regional Approach to the Los
Angeles County Housing Crisis

August 2022

Executive Summary

Los Angeles County faces an affordable housing crisis, one of the most acute in the state of California. Rising rents and home purchase prices, a countywide shortfall of new units to meet current and future demand, old housing stock, and a high proportion of low-wage working families in the metropolitan area have combined to leave too many of the County's residents struggling to secure safe, quality housing. Compounding these trends, the Covid pandemic exacerbated socioeconomic disparities for groups with disproportionately high rates of low-income, especially women of color and single mothers.¹

SB-679, authored by Senator Sydney Kamlager, would create the Los Angeles County Affordable Housing Solutions Agency (LACAHSAs), a countywide multistakeholder agency whose purpose is to increase the supply of affordable housing and provide rental assistance throughout Los Angeles County.²

The [Gender Equity Policy Institute](#) analyzed housing expenditures and income of Los Angeles County residents to assess the disparate gender and race/ethnicity impacts of the regionwide housing affordability crisis. Our findings show that people of color and women, especially Black and Latina women, are more likely to be spending an unsustainable portion of their income on housing.³

Women in Los Angeles County are more likely than men to be paying unaffordable rents

FIGURE 1
GEPI analysis of ACS 2019.

Understanding current racial and gender housing inequities in Los Angeles County, we hope, will assist LACAHSAs in addressing Los Angeles County's regionwide housing crisis in a way that contributes to eliminating existing inequalities, advancing gender and racial equity in housing, and promoting a healthy and sustainable future for all people in Los Angeles County.

KEY FINDINGS

IN LOS ANGELES COUNTY:

- ▶ **53% of women** are rent burdened, compared to 47% of men.
- ▶ **1 in 3 Black women renters** spend more than half their income on housing.
- ▶ **3 in 5 Latino-led households** are rent burdened.
- ▶ **36% of elderly** Latinas living alone have income below the federal poverty line, which is \$12,880 for a single adult.
- ▶ **Women-led households** are 4 times as likely as households headed by a married couple to have extremely low-income.
- ▶ **726,000 children** live in households paying unaffordable rents.

Racial and Gender Disparities in Los Angeles County Housing

The housing affordability crisis is a regional problem. Throughout Los Angeles County, families are paying an unsustainable portion of their income on housing, as seen on the heatmap of rent burden in Figure 2. More than 60% of renters in Santa Clarita, many Gateway cities, and parts of the cities of Long Beach, San Fernando, and Los Angeles have unaffordable housing costs.

GEPI’s analysis of public microdata presents a clear picture that the burden of the region’s high housing costs falls heaviest on people of color and women.⁴

Home ownership rates are particularly low in Los Angeles County, compared to California overall. Nearly six in ten adults in the state live in a home that is owned. But in Los Angeles County, just half do. Children in the County, particularly, are more likely than children statewide to live in a rented home.

Roughly 4.1 million people in Los Angeles County lack affordable housing.⁵ A sizable majority (56%) of renter households in Los Angeles County are rent burdened. Almost a third (31%) are severely rent burdened. Six in ten children living in rentals are in rent burdened households, and one in three are in severely rent burdened households. Homeowners also spend large portions of their income on housing, though compared to renters, a smaller proportion face affordability challenges.⁶

In Los Angeles County, there are notable differences in rent burden by racial/ethnic identification and by gender.

The legacy of racial discrimination in local zoning laws, federal and state housing policy, and mortgage lending policies continues to place obstacles to housing security in the path of people of color. Redlining, restrictive covenants, and freeway development in the past have contributed to spatial and racial segregation in Los Angeles County today. For example, the community known as Sugar Hill was home to middle class black households; these families were displaced to make way for the building of the Santa Monica Freeway.⁷

The affordability crisis is disproportionately borne by people of color. Black people are 9 percentage points more likely than White people to be rent burdened. Latinos are 5 percentage points more likely than White people to be rent burdened. Asian Pacific Islander (API) and White people are about equally likely to be rent burdened. Black, Latino, and API children are more likely than not to be living in a rent burdened household.⁸

Low-income people in Los Angeles County are disproportionately Black or Latino. Latinas have the lowest median income in the County, at \$34,500. The median income of Black women and men is \$50,000. In comparison, the median income of white men in Los Angeles County is \$79,000.⁹

Women are more likely than men to be housing cost burdened and have extremely low incomes.

Households led by women experience both rent burden and severe rent burden at an elevated rate. A third of Black women, nearly a third of White women, and one quarter of Latina and API women spend more than half their income on rent. Thirty percent of elderly women who live alone are poor. One quarter of households headed by women have extremely low income.

Women of every racial/ethnic group are more likely than their male counterparts to be shouldering unaffordable housing costs. Among every race/ethnic group, there is a gender gap in housing affordability,

FIGURE 2
Boundary lines show all Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMA) in Los Angeles County. Blue shading represents percentage of PUMA renters who are rent burdened. On PUMAs, see Methodology section.

with women on average 4.6 points more likely than men to be rent burdened. The gender gap is smallest among API residents (2.2 points) and largest among White residents (6.8 points).

Women are more likely to experience housing affordability challenges for three reasons.

One, on average, women hold less wealth and earn lower incomes; high housing costs are thus more difficult to meet.

Two, a typical accommodation to high housing costs is to move to a more distant but lower cost housing market. For many women, however, this strategy exacerbates the disadvantages they experience due to the gendered division of caregiving labor in the home and occupational segregation in the workforce.

Time use surveys confirm women are more time burdened; they perform the vast majority of childcare, elder care, and household domestic labor. High-paying skilled occupations in the trades, construction, and protective services, are, for all intents and purposes, closed to women. Thus, it is to be expected that women struggle more to pay Los Angeles County's high housing costs.

Three, outright discrimination on the basis of gender, race, and family status, persists in the housing market. In housing assistance programs, for example, landlord rejections of housing vouchers are frequently based on biased stereotypes of women of color in poverty.¹⁰ It is important to underscore that women's current disadvantaged economic status is in large part a legacy of systemic gender discrimination and its interplay with other forms of bias and discrimination. Most women, to some degree, face these societal barriers and disadvantages. But the effects are more acute for women who are also subject to intersecting forms of discrimination—whether on the basis of race, immigration status, age, disability, or family status.

The high cost and low supply of affordable housing throughout Los Angeles County contributes to the increase in the homeless population. In 2021, approximately 77,500 people experienced homelessness in Los Angeles County, 38% of whom

were women or girls. More than a third (36%) were Black people.¹¹

Sexual minority adults have been found to be twice as likely as the overall U.S. population to experience homelessness.¹² Transgender people face an even greater risk of being unhoused. In Los Angeles County, 1.3% of the unhoused are transgender. Additionally, youth aged 18-24 experiencing homelessness in the County are more likely to be female, Black, Latino, or LGBTQ.¹³

Nearly 1 in 5 unhoused Californians report having experienced domestic violence (DV). DV survivors face an array of housing challenges. The difficulty securing alternative shelter and the high cost of housing, research shows, often prevent people from leaving abusers. Landlords have been shown to discriminate against those who have made domestic violence complaints to authorities.¹⁴

LACAHSA Establishes a Foundation for Advancing Equity

By analyzing gender- and race-disaggregated data and drawing on our expertise in gender-responsive housing policy, we are able to assess how a regionwide approach to the housing crisis, based on LACAHSA's specific powers, could powerfully advance equitable solutions to the County's housing crisis.

Certainly, any progress toward increasing the supply of affordable housing and improving renter protections will help alleviate the housing cost burdens on all Los Angeles County residents. The enabling bill (SB-679) goes further; it notes that people of color, especially women of color, are disproportionately harmed by high housing costs. For example, the bill acknowledges the structural barriers faced by women of color, such as wage discrimination, unsafe transit options, and lack of access to affordable childcare, which limit their opportunities and options in the housing market. In several of its components, SB-679 provides workable solutions to the inequities it identifies.

Women of color in Los Angeles County are highly likely to live in areas with unaffordable rents

FIGURE 3

Boundary lines show Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMA). Pink circles represent the percentage of PUMA residents who are people of color. Blue shading represents percentage of PUMA renters who are rent burdened. On PUMAs, see Methodology section.

Dedicated Funds to Develop and Preserve Affordable Housing:

Women and communities of color throughout the County would likely benefit from the increased supply of affordable housing preserved or built from the available funds.

Financing Priority on Lowest Levels of Affordability:

In several programs, SB-679 directs the Agency to target resources to those facing the highest financial barriers to housing stability. For example, rental protections and assistance are focused on “lower-income” households. Support to help households become or remain homeowners is restricted to those with low- or moderate income. Extremely low- and low-income households receive priority in the production and preservation of affordable housing.

Targeting housing assistance to people at the lowest income levels is an appropriate and effective approach to increasing gender and racial equity. Women, especially women of color and elderly women, are more likely to have extremely low incomes. In short, the people who need it most will benefit from these measures with income restrictions.

Collaboration with Los Angeles Metropolitan Transportation Authority (Metro):

In the nexus between transportation and housing, there are many opportunities for advancing gender equity, and formalizing a relationship with Metro is a smart first step in a comprehensive approach. Research shows that women commute differently than men: they travel more frequently, over shorter distances, and use public transportation more. They are more likely to be traveling with children or shopping bags.¹⁵ Being more time-burdened and more dependent on public transportation, the connection between housing and transportation is particularly important to women. Metro has already embarked on gender-responsive planning, and a collaboration with LACAHSAs can be a powerful equity accelerator for both agencies.

Governance and Public Participation:

Research on planning and public participation has stressed the importance of creating inclusive and

The average commute time for Black women who take the bus to work is 2 hours, nearly double the average commute time for Los Angeles County residents who drive to work.¹⁶

transparent multistakeholder-based approaches for government programs.¹⁷ SB-679 establishes several model public engagement and oversight mechanisms. It specifically charges the Board with the responsibility to conduct meaningful public participation and engagement. The bill creates a citizen’s oversight committee and calls for the interim chair to be someone with lived experience of homelessness or housing instability. The remaining members are to be from community-based and advocacy organizations with expertise in housing and substantial ties to communities confronting housing instability. The citizen’s oversight committee is empowered to provide “substantial assistance” in the Board’s development of funding guidelines and implementation of agency programs.

Recommendations

The shortage of affordable housing has detrimental effects on Los Angeles County’s regional economy and quality of life. Nonetheless, as this report documents, people of color and women in Los Angeles County, especially Black and Latina women, are more likely to be paying an unsustainable portion of their income on housing.

The following are seven recommendations for how LACAHSAs, once the Agency is created and begins work, could advance gender and racial equity.

1. Preserve and Develop Affordable Housing in Denser Areas

Low-income workers and women are more likely to be time-burdened, housing-cost burdened, and dependent on public transportation. Locating housing

close to public transit, childcare facilities, essential services, and grocery stores providing good food facilitates workforce participation and quality of life for disadvantaged and marginalized people.

2. Integrate a Gender Lens into Agency Planning

LACAHSA’s authorizing law shows awareness of the disparate impacts of the housing crisis on women, especially women of color. Building on this acknowledgment, the Agency should institutionalize a gender-aware and data-based approach to address inequalities and promote intersectional gender equity in housing. The Agency should cultivate gender expertise within its staff. It should provide technical assistance to local agencies and governments on the best practices for collecting gender- and race disaggregated data related to housing stability. A gender impact assessment should be conducted on any significant funding measure and incorporated into the RFP process. The Agency should explore the development of a scorecard or metrics to assess its progress in closing gender and race/ethnicity equity gaps in Los Angeles County housing.

3. Promote Gender Inclusive and Universal Design Principles in Publicly Supported Housing Development

Housing development has conventionally been geared toward meeting the needs of nuclear families or self-sufficient individuals living alone or in couples, with little consideration given to elderly or disabled people or the needs of caregivers or multigenerational families.

By contrast, a gender-inclusive and universal approach to housing considers the everyday needs of people of all genders, abilities, and ages, with attention to access to jobs, services and retail, childcare, green space, and social space.

In issuing RFPs for creating and preserving affordable housing, the Agency should include a preference for projects incorporating gender-inclusive and universal design principles. Some examples include: a mix of different housing formats, such as multigenerational housing and assisted living facilities; attention to transitional /threshold spaces between public and private, to enhance safety and accessibility for

caregivers, the disabled, and the elderly; energy efficiency; public transit, bike, and pedestrian infrastructure, to provide accessibility for people without cars; convenient access to green and social space.¹⁸

4. Implement a Gender-Responsive Approach to the Unhoused

Women, youth, and LGBTQ+ people face particular vulnerability when they are homeless. Gender-responsive policies and programs can mitigate these challenges. Target policies toward protecting and quickly re-housing domestic violence survivors. For example, integrating, coordinating, and co-locating DV and housing services can increase the likelihood DV survivors secure stable housing.¹⁹

5. Prepare for a Climate-Resilient Future

Review and revise building standards and emergency procedures to protect people from climate impacts, particularly extreme heat. Low-income households are less likely to have air conditioning and more likely to struggle paying energy bills. Craft emergency procedures with the understanding that women are more likely to be responsible for other family members during a crisis and face distinct challenges during evacuations to an emergency shelter. Provide technical assistance and policy recommendations to local agencies regarding the link between housing displacement and climate impacts.

6. Conduct Equity Analyses to Update Housing Services Regulations and Policies

Access to affordable housing services in Los Angeles County has proven difficult for many individuals due to complex reporting systems and bureaucratic processes that create burdens for those seeking available units.²⁰

From many areas of research, it is clear that regulations, policies, and informal practices designed to be “neutral” can have unintended disparate consequences for women, people of color, and marginalized populations. For example, public housing rules often disadvantage women, who are more likely to be responsible for family caregiving. The hours of operation and rules in government offices

can be difficult for single parents who lack childcare support to accommodate; judges, for example, have the power to order children out of courtrooms. The creation of LACAHSAs presents a rare opportunity to dedicate consideration to researching current housing services procedures and developing recommendations for best practices to be shared with local agencies regionwide.

7. A Research Agenda for LACAHSAs

Conducting rigorous data analysis will allow LACAHSAs to understand current inequities in the County’s housing market to inform its decision-making and ensure that resources are equitably distributed. For example, the American Community Survey (ACS) includes data on household size, household type, individual data on all household members, and how many generations live in a household. Using it, LACAHSAs can assess what types and size of housing Los Angeles County needs to support housing security for all residents.

The covid pandemic interrupted data collection at the federal, state, and local levels. In its first year of operation, LACAHSAs should conduct a detailed analysis of the most current demographic, income, and housing data. New data is scheduled to be released from the ACS in October 2022.²¹ Using this and other recent data, LACAHSAs can establish baseline statistics about the housing conditions and needs of Los Angeles County residents. This baseline is vital to establishing specific goals and metrics for work going forward.

Data analysts can assist LACAHSAs in best practices to extract and analyze information collected by state and local agencies, as well as issue recommendations for collecting gender- and race/ethnicity-disaggregated data where the current data is missing these essential variables.

Surveys can supplement data gaps. Public agencies and entities do not necessarily collect all the data at the level that could be helpful in designing housing solutions. While there are important advantages to conducting a well-designed survey by a professional survey firm, LACAHSAs should also consider providing grants for participatory research projects operated through community-based organizations. These

can provide qualitative information about residents’ housing experiences, challenges, and needs and can potentially be targeted at the neighborhood or municipality level.

Methodology

The Gender Equity Policy Institute analyzed microdata from the American Community Survey (2019) and Current Population Survey (2015-2019) to examine how the housing affordability crisis impacts residents of Los Angeles County, with particular attention to disparities by gender and race. Geographic variation in the following trends was estimated at the Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMA) level. PUMAs represent small geographic units with under 200,000 residents. There are 69 PUMAs in Los Angeles County.

2019 is the most recent year for which the data from ACS is reliable. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly impacted the Census Bureau’s ability to collect accurate data, and the Bureau advises that 2020 ACS 1-year estimates do not meet the Census Bureau’s Statistical Data Quality Standards. 2021 data is not yet available, but will be following the October Census release. (<https://www.census.gov/newsroom/press-releases/2021/changes-2020-ac-s-1-year.html>)

Data was collected and analyzed at both the household and individual level. For the household level, we use the U.S. Census classification of household type, which identifies three aggregate categories: households led by married or cohabitating couples (referred to as “joint or joint-led households”), women-led households, and men-led households. We also analyzed data using disaggregated household types, such as single parents, individuals living alone, and individuals with roommates.²²

We define rent burdened households as those spending more than 30% of household income on rental expenses (rent and utilities). Severely rent burdened households are those spending more than 50% of household income on rental expenses. Cost burden and severe cost burden are similarly

calculated for homeownership households, with costs including mortgage payments, property taxes, insurance, and other homeownership expenses.

To analyze household income by gender and race relative to local area median income (AMI), we define income limits according to the thresholds set by the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD): acutely low income, extremely low income, very low income, lower income, moderate income, and above area median income.²³ To be able to analyze the number of households in each income category, disaggregated by gender and race, we use ACS (2019) data to calculate median household incomes in Los Angeles County. Our estimates do not necessarily reflect eligibility for federal housing assistance.

Appendix

**TABLE 1:
COST BURDENED HOUSEHOLDS (%),
BY GENDER, LOS ANGELES**

	All CA	All LA	Joint Led	women Led
Rent Burdened	52%	56%	47%	68%
Severely Rent Burdened	26%	31%	22%	41%
Cost Burdened	29%	34%	29%	45%
Severely Cost Burdened	12%	16%	11%	26%

See Methodology for definition of cost burden levels. GEPI Analysis of ACS (2019).

**TABLE 2:
RENTING AND OWNING HOUSEHOLDS (%),
BY GENDER, LOS ANGELES**

	All CA	All (LA)	Joint Led (LA)	women Led (LA)
Renting Households	45%	55%	45%	63%
Owning Households	55%	45%	55%	37%

See note 7 for definition of household types. GEPI Analysis of ACS (2019).

**TABLE 3:
RENT BURDENED BLACK-LED HOUSEHOLDS (%),
BY GENDER, LOS ANGELES**

	Black-led Households		
	Joint Led	Women Led	Single Mother Led
Rent Burdened	42%	72%	78%
Severely Rent Burdened	17%	43%	51%

Households headed by individuals who identify as Black are defined as Black-led households. Household members can be of any race/ethnicity. Margins of error for these households range from +/- 2-6 percentage points.

**TABLE 4:
RENT BURDENED LATINO-LED HOUSEHOLDS (%),
BY GENDER, LOS ANGELES**

	Latino-led Households		
	Joint Led	Women Led	Single Mother Led
Rent Burdened	52%	70%	77%
Severely Rent Burdened	22%	41%	51%

Households headed by individuals who identify as Latino are defined as Latino-led households. Household members can be of any race/ethnicity.

Sources

¹ Tabashir Z Nobari, Christopher E. Anderson, and Shannon E. Whaley. "The COVID-19 Pandemic Contributed to Disparities in Housing-Cost Burden Among WIC-Participating Households in the Most Populous County in California." *Journal of Racial and Ethnic Health Disparities* (2022): 1-10. doi: 10.1007/s40615-021-01200-7

² "SB-679 Los Angeles County: affordable housing," Pub. L. No. SB-679 (2022), https://leginfo.ca.gov/faces/billNavClient.xhtml?bill_id=202120220SB679.

³ The Gender Equity Policy Institute analyzed American Community Survey (ACS) 2019 household and individual level data accessed through IPUMS USA, University of Minnesota, www.ipums.org. 2019 is the most recent year for which the data from ACS is reliable. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly impacted the Census Bureau's ability to collect accurate data, and the Bureau advises that 2020 ACS 1-year estimates do not meet the Census Bureau's Statistical Data Quality Standards. 2021 data is not yet available, but will be following the October Census release. (<https://www.census.gov/newsroom/press-releases/2021/changes-2020-acs-1-year.html>) For a detailed explanation of the data analysis, see the Methodology. Unless otherwise noted, all estimates and calculations in this report were done by GEPI. (Hereafter GEPI Estimates.)

⁴ We assessed housing affordability in Los Angeles County using three different measures: 1) the number and proportion of individuals, by gender and race, living in rentals or owned homes in which the household is spending above 30% or above 50% of its income on housing; 2) the number and proportion of households, by gender and race and household type, that pay above 30% or above 50% of income on housing; and 3) the proportion of households, by gender and race and household type, that have income levels at or below local area median income (AMI).

⁵ 2.6 million are rent burdened and 1.5 million living in homes that are owned are cost burdened. (GEPI estimates.)

⁶ Housing is considered affordable when no more than 30% of a household's income goes toward housing costs. Those who pay more than 30% are considered rent burdened or, in owner households, cost burdened—and those who pay more than 50% of their income toward housing are considered severely rent burdened or cost burdened. Among homeowners, 31% are cost burdened and 13% are severely cost burdened.

⁷ Richard Rothstein, *The Color of Law: A Forgotten History of How Our Government Segregated America*. (Liveright Publishing, 2017).

⁸ Approximately 21,000 people who identify on the Census as Native American live in Los Angeles County. Sample sizes are too small to reach accurate estimates on their income, housing, and housing cost burden.

⁹ GEPI Estimates.

¹⁰ "Fair Housing in Jeopardy: Trump Administration Undermines Critical Tools for Achieving Racial Equity" (National Fair Housing Alliance, 2020), <https://nationalfairhousing.org/resource/2020-fair-housing-trends-report/>.

¹¹ California Interagency Council on Housing, Homeless Data Integration System, State of California, accessed Jun. 7, 2022, <https://bcsh.ca.gov/calich/hdis.html>. (Hereafter HDIS 2021.)

¹² Sexual minorities include cis and genderqueer lesbian, gay, and bisexual adults. For more information: "Homelessness Among LGBT Adults in the US." UCLA Williams Institute. May 2020. <https://williamsinstitute.law.ucla.edu/publications/lgbt-homelessness-us/>.

¹³ "2020 Greater Los Angeles Homeless Count Presentation." Los Angeles Homeless Services Authority, 2020. <https://www.lahsa.org/documents?id=4558-2020-greater-los-angeles-homeless-count-presentation>; "LAHSA Provides 2020 Update on Youth Homelessness," LAHSA. 2020. <https://www.lahsa.org/news?article=750-lahsa-provides-2020-update-on-youth-homelessness>.

¹⁴ On the nexus between homelessness and domestic violence, see "Fair Housing in Jeopardy"; Isabelle Atkinson, "Housing Justice Is Gender Justice," Issue Brief (National Partnership for Women and Families, March 2022), <https://www.nationalpartnership.org/our-work/resources/economic-justice/housing-justice.pdf>.

¹⁵ Jennifer M. Piscopo, "Gender Mainstreaming in Advanced Industrial Democracies," unpublished report commissioned by GEPI, May 2021.

¹⁶ GEPI Estimates.

¹⁷ Innes, Judith E., and David E. Booher. "Reframing public participation: strategies for the 21st century." *Planning theory & practice* 5, no. 4 (2004): 419-436. doi: 10.1080/1464935042000293170

¹⁸ Viktória Soós, "How Is Vienna 'Gender Mainstreaming'?" (Budapest, Hungary, Central European University, 2008), 44; Women's Advisory Committee of the Senate Department for Urban Development, "Gender Mainstreaming in Urban Development," *Kulturbuch-Verlag GmbH, Berlin*, n.d., 43, https://civitas.eu/sites/default/files/berlin_gender_mainstreaming_o.pdf.

¹⁹ Shanti Joy Kulkarni et al., "Improving Safe Housing Access for Domestic Violence Survivors Through Systems Change," *Housing Policy Debate*, September 9, 2021, 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2021.1947865>; Aleya Jones, Gabriela Sevilla, and F Dylan Waguespack, "State Index on Youth Homelessness," *True Colors United and the National Homelessness Law Center*, 2021, 131.

²⁰ Innes and Booher. "Reframing public participation"; Robin Urevich, "L.A.'s Affordable Housing Programs Leave Low-Income Renters in the Dark." *Capital & Main*, September 7, 2021. <https://capitalandmain.com/l-a-s-affordable-housing-programs-leave-low-income-renters-in-the-dark>

²². The Census identifies twelve categories of households: (1) Married couple household with own children <18, (2) Married couple household, no own children <18, (3) Cohabiting couple household with own children <18, (4) Cohabiting couple household, no own children <18, (5) Female householder, no spouse/partner present, living alone, (6) Female householder, no spouse/partner present, with own children <18, (7) Female householder, no spouse/ partner present, with relatives, no own children <18, and (8) Female householder, no spouse/partner present, only nonrelatives present, (9)) Male householder, no spouse/partner present, living alone, (10) Male householder, no spouse/partner present, with own children <18, (11) Male householder, no spouse/partner present, with relatives, no own children <18, and (12) Male householder, no spouse/partner present, only nonrelatives present.

²³. See "Income Limits," California Department of Housing and Community Development, <https://www.hcd.ca.gov/income-limits>.

About Gender Equity Policy Institute

Our Mission

[Gender Equity Policy Institute](#) is a nonprofit organization dedicated to advancing opportunity, fairness, and well-being for all people through research and education exposing the gender impacts of the policies, processes, and practices of government and business.

Our Work

We conduct and publish research on the best practices for accelerating gender equity. We analyze and rate public policies and business practices to identify the effects on people of all genders, with particular attention to the impacts on groups, such as women, people of color, and LGBTQ+ people, who have been systematically disadvantaged by discrimination, bias, and structural inequality. By educating policymakers, business leaders, and advocates about the inequities embedded in seemingly neutral economic and political processes, we provide the tools and knowledge that leaders need to rebalance systems, guarantee equal benefits and opportunities, and secure a just and sustainable future for all people.

Media Contact

press@thegepi.org

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